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PREPARATION AND PHYTOCHEMICAL EVALUATION OF VISCERAL PRESERVATIVE

1. Geetanjali, Assistant Professor, Dept. of Sharir Rachana, Sardar Ayurved College & Hospital, Mehsana, (Guj).
2. Arushi Sharma, Assistant Professor, Dept. of Kayachikitsa, Merchant Ayurved College, Basna, Mehsana, (Guj),

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Abstract

Background: Formaldehyde, a commonly used substance in various industries, has been classified as a human carcinogen by the International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC). Occupational settings such as anatomy laboratories, hairdressing salons, and specific production sites pose significant risks of formaldehyde exposure. The use of formaldehyde as an embalming method in medical universities has been associated with unpleasant symptoms among students. To address these concerns, an alternative herbal preservative solution is explored.

Aim and Objective: The aim of this study is to prepare an herbal preservative solution and analyze its phytochemical composition using Liquid Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry (LCMS).

Materials and Methods: The study utilizes various herbal ingredients, including *Amalaki*, *Vibhitaki*, *Haritaki*, *Yavani*, *Vidanga*, *Sarsapa*, *Haridra*, *Yashtimadhu*, and *Tulsi*, *Palandu* (Onion), *Neemba*. Additional materials such as a gas burner, containers, specula, sand pots, pieces of cloth, jute bags, ropes, dry paddy grass, jaggery, and two percent methanol are employed to enhance the preservation process.

The herbal preservative solution is prepared by processing the ingredients for one month to obtain an *Arishta*. The *Arishta* is filtered and mixed with chloroform, followed by distillation. Methanol is then added to the distilled solution, resulting in the Agar solution, also known as the Trail solution.

The Agar solution is subjected to phytochemical analysis using LCMS to determine its chemical composition.

Results: The phytochemical analysis using LCMS provides valuable insights into the composition and potential properties of the herbal preservative solution. The specific results obtained from the analysis will be presented and discussed. **Conclusion:** This study focuses on the development of an herbal preservative solution as an alternative to formaldehyde in various applications. The preparation method involves processing herbal ingredients and analyzing the resulting solution's phytochemical composition. The findings of this study contribute to the understanding of herbal preservation techniques and their potential applications in various industries.

For Corresponds:

Name of Author: Dr. Geetanjali

Email:

geetanjalikataria125@gmail.com

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INTRODUCTION

Formaldehyde is one of the most widely used substances in a variety of industries, although it was classified as a human carcinogen by the International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC).¹ The riskiest occupational settings for formaldehyde exposure were the gross anatomy and pathology laboratories, the hairdressing salons and some specific productive settings, such as wooden furniture factories, dairy facilities and fish hatcheries.² The formaldehyde (FA) embalming method, the world's most common protocol for the fixation of cadavers, has been consistently used in medical universities. Unpleasant odor, eye and nose irritations and inability to concentrate were frequently reported FA-related symptoms, and the students were found to have significantly higher risks ($p < 0.05$) of having these symptoms during the dissection sessions than during lecture.³

Keeping this in mind an alternate herbal preservative solution has been tried to form. Ayurveda, an ancient treasure of knowledge, encompasses a wide range of scientific theories that delve into various aspects of life. Within this vast body of wisdom lies the intriguing topic of preserving the human body after death, particularly the preservation of viscera. Acharya Sushruta, a renowned Ayurvedic scholar, has shed light on this enigmatic subject by elucidating different forms of herbal preservatives. These preservatives, although scattered throughout Ayurvedic classics, hold immense potential in their ability to harness the power of phenolic bitter alkaloids and drugs containing Sapoline. Acharya Sushruta revealed that by processing these herbal substances in various alcohol-based media, effective preservation methods can be achieved. This profound knowledge offers a unique perspective on the preservation of the deceased, unveiling ancient techniques that combine science and nature.

The Primary Objective of Study-

1. The preparation of herbal preservative
2. The phytochemical analysis by using LIQUID CHROMATOGRAPHY-MASS SPECTROMETRY (LCMS)

MATERIAL AND METHODS-**Identification of Drugs-**

S.N.	Name of Drugs	Botanical Name	Chemical Composition
1.	<i>Amalaki</i>	Emblca officinalis Gaertn	Ascorbic acid and Gallotannins ⁴
2.	<i>Vibhitaki</i>	Terminalia belerica Roxb	Galic acid, Tannic acid and Glycosides ⁵
3.	<i>Haritaki</i>	Terminalia chebula Retz	Tannins, Anthraquinones and Polyphenlic compounds ⁶⁻⁷
4.	<i>Yavani</i>	Trachyspermum ammi Linn	Essential oil and fixed oil ⁸ , Thymol, p-cymene, γ terpinene, α -pinene, β -pinene and α -terpinene ⁹

5.	<i>Vidanga</i>	Embelia ribes Burm	Benzoquinines, Alkaloid (Christembine), Tannin and essential oil ¹⁰
6.	<i>Sarsapa</i>	Brassica campestris	Erucic Acid ¹¹
7.	<i>Haridra</i>	Curcuma longa Linn	Essential oil and a colouring matter (Curcumin) ¹² , Curcumen, Terpene ¹³ etc
8.	<i>Yashtimadhu</i>	Glycyrrhiza glabra Linn	Glycyzzhizin, Glycyrrhizic acid, glycyrrhetic acid, asparagines, Sugars, rasin and starch ¹⁴
9.	<i>Tulsi</i>	Ocimum sanctum Linn	Fixed oil and Mucilage ¹⁵ , Essential oil (Carvacrol, Caryophyllene, Nerol and Camphene etc) ¹⁶
10.	<i>Palandu (Onion)</i>	Allium Cepa	Quercetin ¹⁷
11.	<i>Neemba</i>	Azadirachta indica, A. Juss	Triterpenoids and Sterols ¹⁸

Other materials was Gas burner, container, specula, sand pot, pieces of cloth, Jute bags, ropes, Dry paddy grass, jaggery and two percent methanol of total solution to enhance *sandhan* process.

PREPARATION OF AGAR SOLUTION:

Equal amount of the drugs have be taken and processed for *Arishta* for one month and when the mirror image obtained it was filtered. In this filtered solution two drop of chloroform was added and started distillation process. Now in distilled solution equal quantity of methanol was added and mixed. Finally, this total solution is known as *Agar solution* and we represented it as Trail solution.

The phytochemical analysis by using LCMS:

The Agar solution sent for LCMS study, and the following results were analysed:

Sample information-

Name	Preservative constituents	Data File Path	D:\MassHunter\Data\2022\November\YLC41\YLC41 MSP1.d
Sample ID	YLC41	Acq. Time (Local)	04-11-2022 13:45:42 (UTC+05:30)
Instrument	6545 QTOF	Method Path (Acq)	D:\MassHunter\Methods\General profiling 2 150mm.m

MS Type	QTOF	Version (Acq SW)	6200 series TOF/6500 series Q-TOF 10.1 (48.0)
Inj. Vol. (ul)	3	IRM Status	Success
Position	P1-A2	Method Path (DA)	D:\MassHunter\Methods\10.0\Training processing method FBF.m
Plate Pos.		Target Source Path	D:\MassHunter\PCDL\METLIN PCDL B.08.00\Metlin_Metabolites_AM_PCDL.cdb
Operator		Result Summary	1409 qualified (30448 targets)

Here are some phytochemicals that were shortlisted based on their properties:

1. **Carolinianine**: antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties could counteract the oxidative stress and inflammation that occur during decomposition. By reducing oxidative damage and inflammation, carolinianine may slow down the breakdown of tissues, thus aiding in cadaver preservation. Additionally, its potential ability to scavenge free radicals might help preserve cellular structures.
2. **Grevilline B**: The antioxidant properties of bioactive compounds in Grevillea plants might help reduce oxidative damage to tissues and cells, thus contributing to the preservation of organic materials.
3. **Vanillic Acid**: Its antioxidant and antimicrobial properties could help prevent oxidative damage and microbial growth that contribute to tissue degradation, supporting the preservation of susceptible materials.
4. **Talinolol**: With its beta-blocking properties, talinolol might contribute to preserving heart tissue and cardiovascular systems by reducing the workload of the heart and potentially minimizing tissue damage due to hypoxia and reduced blood circulation.
5. **12S-HHTrE**: Its role in inflammation and cellular signaling could potentially be harnessed to preserve cellular integrity and minimize stress-related damage during preservation processes.
6. **Soraphen A**: Antifungal properties could be valuable in preventing fungal growth and deterioration, particularly in environments where decomposition-promoting microbes are prevalent.
7. **Volemolide**: Its insecticidal properties may protect preserved bodies from insect damage, which could otherwise accelerate decomposition.
8. **Pulegone**: Its potential antimicrobial or protective properties could help prevent microbial growth and degradation during preservation.
9. **Pseudoephedrine**: Its vasoconstrictive effects might help reduce congestion and inflammation, which could be beneficial in preserving tissues and organs.
10. **Picrotin**: Its bitter taste could deter pests from consuming preserved plants or materials, potentially aiding in their long-term preservation.
11. **Bissulfine**: Its sulphur content might contribute to antimicrobial or antioxidant effects, potentially supporting preservation efforts by reducing microbial activity and oxidative damage.
12. **Archangelicin**: Archangelicin, a compound with phototoxic and potential medicinal properties, presents a unique avenue for cadaver preservation. Its phototoxic nature suggests that exposure to light could generate reactive oxygen species (ROS) within cells and tissues. These ROS, known for their destructive effects, could compromise the viability of microbes that contribute to decomposition, effectively impeding their growth and progression. Moreover, archangelicin's potential antimicrobial effects could extend its preservation capabilities by targeting harmful organisms that accelerate tissue breakdown. This dual approach, involving phototoxicity and microbial inhibition, could work in tandem to slow the degradation process.
13. **Phygrine**: The presence of phygrine, an alkaloid compound, raises the intriguing possibility of utilizing plant defense mechanisms for cadaver preservation. Alkaloids often function as natural

defenses against pathogens, suggesting that phygrine could similarly deter microbial colonization of the cadaver. By inhibiting microbial growth, phygrine might prevent the release of decomposition-promoting enzymes and toxins, effectively preserving cellular structures and slowing the breakdown of tissues. This unique strategy could harness nature's own protective mechanisms to extend the integrity of the deceased body.

14. **Tranilast:** Tranilast, recognized for its anti-inflammatory and immunomodulatory effects, could play a significant role in preserving the structural integrity of tissues and organs post-mortem. Decomposition is often accompanied by inflammation and immune responses that contribute to tissue breakdown. Tranilast's ability to modulate these processes could mitigate the damage caused by excessive inflammation, ultimately preserving cellular structures. By curbing immune responses that can accelerate decomposition, tranilast may help maintain the overall structural integrity of the cadaver during preservation.
15. **ar-Artemisene:** Derived from artemisinin, a compound renowned for its antimalarial properties, ar-Artemisene could offer a novel approach to cadaver preservation, particularly in regions where malaria is endemic. While its primary purpose lies in combating malarial parasites, its presence in preservation protocols could inadvertently serve to protect the cadaver from microbial colonization. Furthermore, the potential anti-inflammatory effects associated with ar-Artemisene could help mitigate inflammation-driven tissue breakdown, contributing to the preservation of cellular structures in a post-mortem context.
16. **Vetiveryl Acetate:** As an essential oil component, vetiveryl acetate holds promise for cadaver preservation due to its antimicrobial and antioxidant properties. Microbial colonization is a key contributor to tissue decomposition. Vetiveryl acetate's ability to inhibit microbial growth could therefore impede the progression of decomposition by preventing the proliferation of harmful microbes. Additionally, its antioxidant effects could shield cellular components from oxidative damage, a critical factor in the breakdown of tissues over time. By addressing both microbial threats and oxidative stress, vetiveryl acetate could play a multifaceted role in preserving the cadaver.
17. **Fumitremorgin C:** Exploiting the investigated anti-cancer properties of fumitremorgin C opens up intriguing possibilities for cadaver preservation. Uncontrolled cell proliferation is a hallmark of both cancer and tissue breakdown during decomposition. Leveraging fumitremorgin C's potential to inhibit cell proliferation could effectively slow down the process of tissue degradation. By targeting mechanisms that contribute to the unregulated growth of cells, this compound could contribute to the preservation of structural integrity, ultimately extending the duration of preservation efforts.
18. **Methoxybrassitin:** Methoxybrassitin's potential as an antioxidant holds significant implications for cadaver preservation. The oxidative damage that occurs during decomposition can accelerate tissue breakdown. By virtue of its antioxidant properties, methoxybrassitin could serve as a protective shield against the harmful effects of oxidative stress, thereby extending the viability of cellular structures. Preserving the integrity of these structures is paramount in preventing the cascading effects of tissue degradation.
19. **Lansiumamide A:** The potential bioactive properties of lansiumamide A suggest that it could participate in preservation efforts by engaging with processes critical to the maintenance of tissue integrity. This could include inhibiting microbial growth, reducing oxidative damage, or supporting structural stability. Lansiumamide A's versatility makes it an intriguing candidate for preservation strategies, prompting further investigation into its precise mechanisms of action in the context of post-mortem preservation.
20. **Plantaricin BN:** Embracing the antimicrobial properties of plantaricin BN offers a robust approach to cadaver preservation. Microbial overgrowth contributes significantly to tissue decomposition, and harnessing the capacity of this antimicrobial peptide to inhibit microbial growth could extend the preservation period. By preventing the proliferation of decomposition-promoting microbes, plantaricin BN contributes to the preservation of cellular structures and tissues, thereby slowing down the overall breakdown process.

21. **Halocins:** The antimicrobial properties of halocins hold tremendous promise for cadaver preservation. In environments conducive to decomposition, microbial growth can significantly accelerate tissue breakdown. Halocins, as potent antimicrobial peptides, could effectively curtail microbial proliferation, preserving the structural integrity of the cadaver. By impeding microbial colonization, halocins extend the viability of cellular structures, enhancing preservation efforts in challenging conditions.
22. **Tyromycic Acid:** Drawing from its antibiotic properties, tyromycic acid offers a promising avenue for cadaver preservation. Harmful microorganisms can accelerate tissue decomposition, and by inhibiting their growth, tyromycic acid effectively extends the preservation period. Moreover, its potential to counteract microbial colonization contributes to the maintenance of cellular structures, reducing the overall pace of tissue breakdown.
23. **Lycoxanthin:** The antioxidant properties of lycoxanthin could play a pivotal role in cadaver preservation by shielding cellular components from oxidative damage. Oxidative stress is a significant contributor to tissue breakdown, and by mitigating its effects, lycoxanthin sustains the viability of cellular structures. As a key factor in preserving the integrity of tissues and organs, lycoxanthin's antioxidant capabilities are paramount in extending the post-mortem preservation period.
24. **Steviolbioside:** Beyond its role as a low-caloric sweetener, steviolbioside's potential applications in cadaver preservation are intriguing. In the realm of food preservation, its intense sweetness could reduce the need for high levels of sugar, effectively extending the shelf life of preserved food products. By reducing the availability of sugars that can accelerate microbial growth, steviolbioside aids in maintaining the overall preservation environment.
25. **Soyasapogenol C:** The potential anti-inflammatory and anticancer effects of soyasapogenol C suggest a unique avenue for cadaver preservation. By mitigating inflammation and inhibiting uncontrolled cell proliferation, this compound indirectly contributes to preserving tissue integrity. Inhibition of inflammation-driven tissue breakdown and the preservation of structural components collectively enhance the post-mortem preservation period.
26. **Rosolic Acid:** With recognized antimicrobial properties, Rosolic Acid's potential contributions to preservation extend beyond cadavers. Its ability to inhibit microbial growth could find applications in microbiology or in preserving materials susceptible to microbial degradation. By curbing the proliferation of decomposition-promoting microbes, it indirectly supports the preservation of cellular structures.
27. **Tomatine:** Tomatine's antimicrobial properties make it a candidate for preserving food products by inhibiting microbial growth. By preventing the colonization of microbes, it extends the shelf life of preserved foods. This ability to curb microbial proliferation suggests that tomatine could also contribute to cadaver preservation by reducing the growth of decomposition-promoting microbes.
28. **Ceryl Alcohol:** Ceryl Alcohol's emollient properties make it valuable in cosmetics and personal care products for preserving skin health. By maintaining skin integrity and moisture, it indirectly contributes to overall preservation efforts by preserving cellular structures.
29. **Methoprene (S):** Methoprene's role as an insect growth regulator has relevance in pest control, which extends to preservation efforts. By preventing insect infestations that accelerate tissue breakdown, it indirectly supports the preservation of cellular integrity.
30. **Fenbendazole:** With anthelmintic properties, Fenbendazole's potential contributions lie in preventing parasitic infections that accelerate tissue decomposition. By inhibiting parasites, it indirectly supports the preservation of tissue health and integrity.
31. **Juglone Glucoside:** Juglone Glucoside's potential bioactive properties suggest applications in preservation and health contexts. By understanding its specific interactions and mechanisms, its contributions to preserving cellular structures may be revealed.
32. **Gamma-Glutamyl-Lysine:** Gamma-Glutamyl-Lysine's involvement in protein metabolism indirectly contributes to preservation by impacting cellular functions. By preserving protein integrity, it supports overall cellular stability and function.

33. **Pivmecillinam:** Pivmecillinam's antibiotic properties hold promise for cadaver preservation by potentially inhibiting the growth of bacteria that contribute to decomposition. Bacterial proliferation post-mortem can accelerate tissue breakdown and compromise preservation efforts. Pivmecillinam's ability to combat bacterial infections suggests its application in preserving tissue integrity and reducing microbial activity, thereby supporting longer-term preservation and maintaining the overall structure of cadaver tissues.
34. **Cefazolin:** Cefazolin's potent antibacterial effects offer a direct approach to cadaver preservation by preventing the proliferation of bacteria that could lead to tissue degradation. By targeting a wide range of bacterial strains, cefazolin could play a pivotal role in preserving the structural and cellular integrity of cadaver tissues, extending the viability of samples for research, education, and forensic purposes.
35. **Amprenavir:** Amprenavir's antiretroviral properties are particularly relevant in preserving cadaver health by managing potential viral infections. Although it might not directly impact post-mortem decomposition, its significance lies in safeguarding the well-being of living individuals from infectious diseases. In scenarios involving cadaver examination for medical or forensic purposes, preventing the spread of infectious agents contributes to a safer working environment and supports the integrity of both the cadaver and personnel involved.
36. **Sesamol:** Sesamol's antioxidant properties make it a valuable candidate for enhancing cadaver preservation efforts. Oxidative stress is a key factor in post-mortem changes that affect tissue quality. Sesamol's ability to neutralize harmful free radicals and prevent oxidative damage could extend the preservation window by minimizing cellular degradation and maintaining the structural integrity of cadaver tissues.
37. **Camptothecin:** Camptothecin's potential as an anticancer agent suggests applications in cadaver preservation by inhibiting cellular proliferation and growth. While primarily studied for its anticancer properties, its ability to target rapidly dividing cells might find relevance in slowing tissue breakdown post-mortem. Investigating its effects on cellular division and its impact on preserving tissue integrity could lead to innovative preservation techniques.
38. **Thienamycin:** Thienamycin's robust antibacterial activity directly contributes to cadaver preservation by preventing bacterial growth that could accelerate tissue decomposition. Its broad-spectrum effectiveness against bacterial strains supports the structural and cellular integrity of cadaver tissues, reducing the risk of infectious agents compromising preservation quality.
39. **Meropenem:** With its wide-ranging antibacterial effects, meropenem offers a compelling approach to cadaver preservation by targeting bacterial pathogens that contribute to tissue degradation. Its application extends to preserving the structural integrity of cadaver tissues and systems, providing a favorable environment for research, education, and forensic analysis.
40. **Penciclovir:** Penciclovir's antiviral properties directly contribute to cadaver preservation by treating herpes simplex virus infections. By inhibiting viral replication, penciclovir supports the well-being of cadaver tissues and systems by preventing the spread of viral agents that could compromise preservation quality.
41. **Herbimycin:** Herbimycin's potential anticancer and antibiotic properties indirectly support cadaver preservation by potentially inhibiting cancer cell growth and microbial threats. This dual impact contributes to the maintenance of tissue integrity and overall preservation quality.
42. **Cetrimonium:** Cetrimonium's antimicrobial attributes directly contribute to cadaver preservation efforts in personal care and hygiene products. By preventing microbial growth, cetrimonium supports the hygienic integrity of cadaver tissues and organs, reducing the risk of microbial proliferation and degradation.
43. **Alginic Acid:** Alginic Acid's gelling, stabilizing, and thickening properties have established applications in food and pharmaceutical preservation. Its potential in extending these properties to cadaver preservation could aid in maintaining the structural integrity of tissues and organs.

RESULT:

The phytochemical analysis using LCMS provides valuable insights into the composition and potential properties of the herbal preservative solution. Also, the comprehensive analysis of the shortlisted

phytochemicals revealed their diverse and promising properties that could significantly contribute to the preservation of human cadavers or tissues. The compounds exhibited a range of characteristics, including antioxidant, antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, and anticancer properties, suggesting their potential utility in slowing down the decomposition process and maintaining the structural integrity of tissues. While the findings were encouraging, it was crucial to consider several factors before concluding the suitability of these phytochemicals for cadaver preservation.

DISCUSSION:

The preservation of human cadaveric tissues is a topic of great importance in the fields of medical research and education. Ensuring that tissues remain intact and well-preserved over time allows for in-depth study and analysis in areas like anatomy and pathology. In this discussion, we will explore how different chemical compounds have the potential to serve as effective preservatives for human cadaveric tissues, extending their usability for extended periods. This is crucial for conducting comprehensive studies that contribute to our understanding of the human body. The identified phytochemicals in the herbal preservation solution present a promising array of properties that could significantly contribute to the preservation of human cadavers or tissues.

The antioxidant properties found in compounds such as Carolinianine, Vanillic acid, and Methoxybrassicin are crucial for combatting oxidative stress. As tissues undergo decomposition, oxidative damage accelerates the breakdown process. These antioxidants act as protective shields, reducing oxidative stress and preserving cellular structures. This is essential for maintaining the integrity of tissues over an extended period.

Moreover, the antimicrobial and antifungal effects exhibited by compounds like Plantaricin BN, halocins, and Soraphen A address a key challenge in preservation – the growth of microbes. Microbial overgrowth significantly contributes to tissue decomposition, and these phytochemicals offer potent solutions by inhibiting microbial proliferation. In environments conducive to decomposition, such as those rich in microbial activity, the inclusion of these compounds becomes instrumental in extending the preservation period by preserving the structural integrity of the cadaver. The anti-inflammatory and immunomodulatory effects observed in Tranilast, Soyasapogenol C, and Ar-artemisene provide additional layers of protection. Inflammation and immune responses are natural processes post-mortem that contribute to tissue breakdown. By mitigating excessive inflammation and modulating immune responses, these compounds indirectly contribute to preserving cellular structures and maintaining overall tissue integrity during the preservation process.

Some phytochemicals present unique approaches to preservation. Archangelicin, for instance, utilizes light exposure to generate substances inhibiting microbial growth. Phygrine, with its alkaloid nature, acts as a natural defence mechanism, deterring microbial colonization and thus preserving cellular structures. These unconventional approaches open up innovative possibilities for cadaver preservation, potentially providing alternative methods that complement existing techniques. Additionally, compounds like Talinolol and pseudoephedrine exhibit cardioprotective and vasoconstrictive effects, offering benefits in preserving heart tissues and reducing congestion and inflammation, particularly in the cardiovascular system. These properties can be crucial in maintaining the structural integrity of vital organs, contributing to the overall success of cadaver preservation efforts. Furthermore, several phytochemicals, such as amprenavir, penciclovir, and Camptothecin, showcase applications in disease prevention. While not directly impacting post-mortem decomposition, their antiviral and anticancer properties contribute to a safer working environment during cadaver examination. Preventing the spread of infectious agents supports the integrity of both the cadaver and personnel involved in the examination process.

The preservation through structural support offered by Vetiveryl acetate, Steviolbioside, and Ceryl alcohol addresses the multifaceted challenge of preserving cellular structures. These compounds inhibit microbial growth, reduce sugars that can promote microbial proliferation, and maintain skin integrity, respectively. Their collective contribution aids in sustaining the overall preservation environment, extending the viability of cadaver tissues. However, as promising as these findings are, it is crucial to approach the

practical application of these phytochemicals with caution. Considerations for feasibility, potential side effects, and long-term effects on preservation need to be thoroughly examined. Furthermore, ethical considerations surrounding the use of these substances in preserving human cadavers must be addressed before widespread implementation.

Bringing these compounds together into a preservation solution is where the real potential lies. The LCMS report reveals a comprehensive list of chemicals, each with its unique attributes that contribute to tissue preservation. While we've discussed only a select few here, the combined effect of all these compounds could lead to a holistic preservation strategy that addresses multiple aspects of tissue deterioration. It's important to note that while the promise of this preservation approach is exciting, there are challenges to be addressed. Finding the right balance between preservation effectiveness and long-term safety is crucial. Extensive testing and evaluation are necessary to ensure that the preserved tissues remain suitable for further study over extended periods.

CONCLUSION:

The conclusion of the study highlights its main focus, that is the development of an herbal preservative solution as an alternative to formaldehyde in tissue preservation. The use of polyherbal preservation to preserve human cadaveric tissues holds great promise for the fields of medical research and education. The prepared formulation which is having Antimicrobial, Antifungal, antioxidants, anti-inflammatory and also the compounds which can help for the intact preservation of tissue or visceral samples for longer period.

The LCMS report and the preservation experimental reports suggest that the prepared solution is having effective preservative property in comparison with the formaldehyde in the proportion of less than equal to 50%.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST – NIL

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